

Double Alkoxides containing Antimony and Alkali Metals*

SHUVENDU CHATTERJEE** and D. D. BHATNAGAR

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan

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A series of double isopropoxides $MSb(OPr^1)_4$ (where $M=Li, Na$ or K), containing two different metals (trivalent antimony and corresponding alkali metals) has been isolated by the addition of the corresponding alkali metal in the molar ratio 1 : 1 to isopropoxy antimonite dissolved in an excess of parent alcohol. The derivatives containing sodium or potassium, $MSb(OPr^1)_4$ (where $M=Na$ or K), were found to be monomeric ebullioscopically in boiling benzene, whereas the derivative containing lithium was found to be insoluble in benzene and parent alcohol. Some tert-alkoxy derivatives $KSb(OR^1)_4$ (where $R^1=Bu^t$ and $Pent^t$) have also been isolated by the alkoxy interchange reactions.

A good number of metal alkoxides¹⁻⁴ have been found to be polymeric due to the capability of alkoxy groups to act as a bridge between two metal atoms, which helps the central metal atom to achieve higher coordinated state as well. Recently a good number of double alkoxides^{5,6}, $MM'(OR)_{n+n'}$, have been isolated and studied, in which two different metals M and M' , having valencies n and n' respectively, have been linked together with the aid of alkoxy bridges^{5,6}.

In comparison to metal alkoxides¹⁻⁴ having metal-oxygen-carbon bonds, the isolation and study of metal-sulphur-carbon bonded thiol derivatives^{7,8} are of recent interest. The capability of alkylthio groups to act as a bridge between two metal atoms has also been observed in a good number of polymeric thiol derivatives^{7,8}. Recently some double thiol derivatives containing two different metals $MIn(SR)_4$ (where $M=Li, Na$ or K and $R=Pr$ or Bu) and $MSb(SBu^t)_4$ (where $M=Li, Na$ or K) have also been isolated and studied^{8,12}.

In view of the above, the isolation and study of a novel series of double alkoxides containing trivalent antimony and alkali metals have been undertaken.

Experimental

These compounds were extremely susceptible to hydrolysis. Special precautions were, therefore, taken to exclude moisture from all the apparatus and chemicals used in every step of the synthesis^{8,15,16}.

Preparation of isopropoxyantimonite: Isopropoxyantimonite was prepared by "ammonia method" under rigorously moisture-free conditions¹⁶:

The colourless fuming liquid was finally distilled under reduced pressure (b.p. 120.0°/6 mm.) before use. (Analysis: found $Sb, 40.69$, $-OPr^1gr, 59.10\%$; calcd. for $Sb(OPr^1)_3, Sb, 40.75$, $-OPr^1gr, 59.25\%$).

Analytical procedure adopted: Antimony(III) and alkoxy groups or alcohols liberated were estimated by oxidimetric methods^{19,20,21}.

Isolations of double isopropoxides: A weighed amount of isopropoxy antimonite¹⁶ was allowed to dissolve in isopropanol. A calculated amount of alkali metal (in the molar ratio 1 : 1) was added to it, and the contents were shaken thoroughly. It was refluxed in a very low flame for a few hours to complete the reaction. The excess of the alcohol was removed by distillation, and the solid was finally dried under vacuo. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

Alcoholysis of $KSb(OPr^1)_4$ with tert-butanol: The double isopropoxide (1.56 g) containing potassium was dissolved in benzene (20 ml). An excess of tert-butanol (about 10 g) was added. The contents of the flask were refluxed for 3 hrs. Azeotrope was collected at about 72°, and the excess of solvent was removed at 80°. A brown crystalline powder was obtained, which was finally dried at 25.0°/0.5 mm for 2 hrs. Analysis: Found, $Sb, 26.78\%$, calcd. for $KSb(OPr^1)_4, Sb, 26.88\%$. Pr^1OH in azeotrope, 3.87 moles (calcd. 4 moles).

Alcoholysis of $KSb(OPr^1)_4$ with tert-pentanol: The double isopropoxide (1.67 g) containing potassium was dissolved in benzene (20 ml). An excess of tert-pentanol (about 10 g) was added to it when a clear yellow solution was obtained. The contents were refluxed for two hrs, azeotrope was removed as usual and was estimated^{18,19}. A brown crystalline mass was obtained on drying at 30°/0.5 mm, for 2 hrs. Analysis: Found, $Sb, 23.65\%$; calcd. for $KSb(OPent^t)_4, Sb, 23.93\%$.

The results have been summarised in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The double isopropoxides $MSb(OPr^1)_4$ containing antimony(III) and alkali metals have been isolated by the addition of the corresponding alkali metals ($M=Li, Na$ or K) in a molar ratio 1 : 1 to isopropoxides¹⁶ dissolved in an excess of parent alcohol. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

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** Present address: Department of Chemistry, Tata College, Chaibasa-833 202, Ranchi University, Bihar.

TABLE 1—PREPARATIONS AND PROPERTIES OF DOUBLE ALKOXIDES MSb(OPr^t)₄

Sl. No.	Sb(OPr ^t) ₄ taken (in gms)	Pr ^t OH added (in mls)	Alkali metal added (in gms)	Yield Obt'd.	Analysis Sb%		Formula wt. and nature of the product	Determined Mol. wt. in boiling benzene	
					Calcd.	Found		Calcd.	Found
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	7.185	40	Lithium (0.141)	89%	33.38	33.34	LiSb(OPr ^t) ₄ Snow-white solid	865.04	Insoluble in boiling benzene and alcohol
2.	8.09	40	Sodium (0.616)	73%	31.98	31.68	NaSb(OPr ^t) ₄ White solid	390.75	386
3.	10.64	40	Potassium (1.04)	96%	30.67	29.75	KSb(OPr ^t) ₄ White solid	336.75	403
								377.196	

TABLE 2—ALCOHOLYSIS OF KSb(OPr^t)₄

Sl. No.	Wt. of KSb(OPr ^t) ₄ taken (g)	Alcohol added (in g)	Analysis Sb%		Pr ^t OH in azeotrope		Formula and nature of the product
			Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.	1.56 g	Bu ^t OH 10 g	26.83	26.78	4 Moles	3.97 Moles	KSb(OBu ^t) ₄ A brown crystalline powder. Soluble in benzene.
2.	1.65 g	Pent ^t OH 10 g	23.93	23.63	4 Moles	3.90 Moles	KSb(OPent ^t) ₄ A brown crystalline powder. Soluble in benzene.

On the contrary, a similar attempt to isolate the doublethiol derivative^{11,12} by the addition of alkali metals to alkylthioantimonites^{7,10} dissolved in an excess of parent primary or secondary thiols, did not lead to successful results probably due to the dominating reducing properties of these primary and secondary thiols alongwith the liberated hydrogen^{11,12}.

Moreover, the alkylthioantimonites⁸⁻¹⁰ derived from primary and secondary thiols have been found to undergo decomposition in contact with atmospheric oxygen even under rigorously moisture free conditions, whereas alkoxyantimonites¹⁶ remain inactive towards dry oxygen at room temperature and ordinary pressure^{13,14} though these alkoxy derivatives are very much sensitive to moisture.

In view of the comparative stability of tert-butylthioantimonite⁹⁻¹¹ with respect to other alkylthioantimonites⁸⁻¹⁰ derived from various primary and secondary thiols towards air and moisture^{13,14} (probably due to the poorer reducing nature of tert-butanethiol or tert-butylthio groups^{11,12}), the double thiol derivatives MSb(SBu^t)₄ (where M = Li, Na or K) could be isolated from the tert-butylthio derivative only⁹⁻¹⁰.

The double isopropoxide containing lithium has been found to be snow-white solid, and the derivatives containing sodium and potassium are white solid. Although the greater covalent character of a number of lithium compounds in comparison to those of sodium and potassium is pretty well known^{11,12}, the double isopropoxide containing lithium was found to be insoluble in benzene, and parent alcohol, whereas the derivatives containing sodium and potassium were soluble in parent

alcohol and benzene, in which these were found to be monomeric ebullioscopically.

The double alkoxydes containing aluminium and lithium or sodium were also practically insoluble in isopropanol and benzene⁸ whereas potassium aluminium isopropoxide has been reported⁸ to be soluble in isopropanol.

The analogous double thiol derivative LiSb(SBu^t)₄ was monomeric ebullioscopically in boiling chloroform^{11,12}, whereas the derivatives containing sodium or potassium were insoluble in the parent thiol, and all other common organic solvents.

Alcoholysis reactions: Alcoholysis reactions^{1-4,15} are used for the synthesis of higher alkoxy derivatives of various metals, and are usually carried out in benzene, when the liberated alcohol is fractionated out azeotropically and estimated oxidimetrically^{18,19} to establish the completion of the reaction.

In the present investigation, some tert-alkoxy derivatives have been isolated from the double alkoxydes containing potassium:

The double alkoxydes, KSb(OBu^t)₄ and KSb(OPent^t)₄ were found to be brown crystalline solids. The interchangeable (labile) nature of the alkoxy groups present in these double alkoxydes also become apparent from these alcoholysis reactions.

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